

SHAKUNTALA: THE PLAY OF MEMORY - AN ECO-FEMINIST READING

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ABSTRACT

There may hardly be any disagreement that all popular cultures are of male dominance. Females' subordination is normalized by various norms that are full of assumptions and prejudices. Things have historically been, to a large extent, put at 'right' place from a male perspective. In various societies across the world 'voices', over the long period of time, that questioned and argued against these norms led to a social and political movement: feminism.

*Eco-feminism is a subset of feminism and it has a strong 'feeling' that the patriarchy has adversely affected the environment and ecology also. The 'exploitation' of 'female' and 'natural resources' are interrelated. These issues of subordination and exploitation are raised in eco-feminist writings. This research looks at Namita Gokhale's *Shakuntala: The Play of Memory* from an eco-feminist perspective to see to what extent the story in the novel raises important eco-feminist concerns. It aims at identifying the explicit and implicit instances of feminist and eco-feminist issues in the text. It explores into how Gokhale reclaims the mythological figure of Shakuntala, transforming her from a passive character into one with agency, closely tied to the rhythms of nature.*

*This Shakuntala is different from the mythical one depicted in the Mahabharata and Kalidasa's *Abhijnanasakuntalam*. Gokhale critiques the historical and cultural narratives that have justified both environmental degradation and the oppression of women by retelling the story of Shakuntala myth from an eco-feminist perspective. The protagonist's connection to the natural world, particularly the forest, symbolizes her resistance to patriarchal structures and reflects the broader eco-feminist critique of domination. The novel's exploration of memory parallels the degradation of the environment, as protagonist's fragmented recollections mirror the broken relationship between humans and nature. Gokhale's *Shakuntala* offers a powerful commentary on the interconnectedness of women's and nature's struggles under patriarchal systems.*

Key Terms: Eco-feminist, exploitation, patriarchy, environment, nature, memory

Paper Type: Research Paper

INTRODUCTION

Namita Gokhale's *Shakuntala: The Play of Memory* is a multifaceted description that mingles personal memory (of one's life) with that of the mythological references available for that name. This novel primarily explores themes of identity, nature, and femininity. The protagonist, Shakuntala, is more than just a character drawn from Indian mythology. She is a metaphor, in a sense, for the modern woman navigating the patriarchal structures of society and the environmental degradation. It echoes the subjugation of women. The themes make this novel an ideal text for an eco-feminist reading. It views the exploitation of nature and the oppression of women as interconnected.

According to Karen Warren, eco-feminism recognizes the links between the oppression of females and the exploitation of nature. Historically, scholars agree that eco-feminism, as a theory, emerged in the 1970s during the environmental and feminist movements. Françoise d'Eaubonne coined the term. Indian eco-feminist Vandana Shiva has expanded on this theory in the context of developing nations, where women, especially rural women, are often the first victims of environmental degradation. As stated above, this paper explores *Shakuntala: The Play of Memory* through an eco-feminist lens, focusing on themes such as the connection between women and nature, the role of memory and identity, and the reclamation of feminine power through subverting the mythical story of Shakuntala.

Theoretical Construction: Eco-Feminism

The emergence of eco-feminism as a literary doctrine and a social view point was in the late 20th century as a response to the dual exploitations of women and nature. The patriarchal system, which values authority and control, has historically treated both women and nature as 'resources' to be used and exploited. It has been asserted that the intellectuals such as Vandana Shiva and Maria Mies have been influential in advocating the eco-feminist perspective. They have been arguing that the same patriarchal structures are responsible for the subjugation of women that lead to environmental deprivation. As Shiva (1989) positions, "The marginalization of women and the destruction of biodiversity go hand in hand," stressing on the interconnectedness of these issues of gender and nature.

Eco-Feminist theory asserts that a feminist perspective on ecology does not place women in a dominant position of power, but requires an egalitarian and collaborative society in which there is no group domination.

Eco-feminism finds a place within contemporary democratic theory. It illustrates its potential to reveal the limitations and deficiencies in politics, ethics, and knowledge. It challenges hegemonic identities and opens new spaces for social, political, and ecological scrutiny. It allows for the examination of the discursive relations that embed problematic gender and ecological relations. Nevertheless, eco-feminism maintains a focus on materialist analysis and praxis committed to hierarchical relationships, dialogical engagement, and situated knowledge.

By the 1990s, critical theory had moved toward dispersal, eclecticism, and special interest forms of criticism and theory. Postmodernism emphasized the fragmented nature of contemporary

experience, feminism and eco-feminism evolved into gender studies, and the literature of marginalized voices, including gay and lesbian studies, gained prominence. Eco-feminism examines the oppression of both the natural world and women by patriarchal power structures. There is a recognized connection between nature and literature, with the natural environment and ecology playing significant roles in literary traditions. Humans are inherently linked to nature, interacting with it daily through the air we breathe, the water we drink, the food we eat, and the energy and information we receive. Literature, as a reflection of the world in which humans live and grow, has always shown a close relationship with nature.

Carolyn Merchant, in *The Death of Nature*, discusses how the scientific revolution contributed to the mechanistic view of nature, where both women and the environment were seen as passive objects to be controlled and manipulated (Merchant, 1980). This objectification has led to the exploitation of natural resources and the marginalization of women, particularly in rural and indigenous communities. Eco-feminists argue for a paradigm shift towards a more holistic and interconnected understanding of life. The need for a deep ecological awareness is emphasized. This distinguishes the inherent values of all living organisms and the interconnectedness of life systems on the earth.

It is to argue that women are seen closer to nature due to their reproductive capabilities, and thus, both face subjugations by very similar forms of control. Vandana Shiva explains in *Staying Alive*, "the patriarchal mindset views both women and nature as passive, devoid of agency, and thus ripe for exploitation" (Shiva 15). In the context of India, this connection between women and nature is particularly strong, as women are often the primary caretakers in rural societies as they are responsible for gathering water, firewood, and food from the natural surroundings. Thus, the degradation of the nature directly affects women's ability to work effectively to support their families and communities.

'Shakuntala' in Indian Mythology

A reader cannot fully comprehend and understand Gokhale's reconstruction of Shakuntala without looking at and examining the character's origins in Indian mythology. Shakuntala, as depicted in the *Mahabharata* and the sage poet Kalidasa's *Abhijnanasakuntalam*, is a symbol of purity, love, and devotion. This mythical lady is born in a forest. She is nurtured by the sage Kanva, symbolizing her intrinsic connection to the natural world. Her story revolves around her love for King Dushyanta, her subsequent rejection, and her eventual reunion with her love after King Dushyanta recovers his memory. At surface it seems a fairy tale of love but the sufferings of Shakuntala are unbearable.

In the traditional texts as stated above, Shakuntala is often shown a passive, a victim of circumstances that are beyond her control. It is important to note in this regard here that in a subtle way, her connection to nature is emphasized. This is done through her upbringing in the forest, yet she is eventually removed from this environment. She is thrust into the patriarchal world of the luxurious palace where her values are determined by her relationship with her husband king Dushyanta.

Gokhale's *Shakuntala: The Play of Memory* 'reads' and reinterprets this mythical feminine being in a way that empowers Shakuntala. This novel gives her agency and places her connection to nature at the forefront of her identity. The change in the perspective allows for a deeper exploration of eco-feminist themes in the novel. Gokhale's *Shakuntala*'s story becomes not just about personal loss and reunion but about the broader struggles of all women and nature under the system of patriarchal domination.

Shakuntala: An Eco-Feminist Creation

In *Shakuntala: The Play of Memory*, Gokhale creates a central character who is deeply connected to nature. This connection is much like her mythological counterpart. Indeed, the novel's *Shakuntala* is not just a passive recipient of nature's gift. She is an active participant in its rhythms and cycles. As Gokhale writes, "Shakuntala's spirit was tied to the rhythms of the forest, her movements mirroring the sway of the trees and the flow of the river" (Gokhale 56). This connection to nature is central to her identity. This positions her as a symbol of eco-feminist resistance.

The novel beautifully showcases the forest as a feminine space. Forest is one that is nurturing, life-sustaining, and free from the constraints of patriarchal society. It is the forest, the nature, where *Shakuntala* experiences a sense of freedom and autonomy, away from the social structures that pose to control her. Eco-feminist scholars such as Carolyn Merchant have argued that the patriarchal system often constructs a binary opposition between nature (associated with women) and culture (associated with men), with the latter seen as superior and in need of dominating the former. In this novel traditional binary is subverted, as the forest becomes a space of power and society for *Shakuntala*.

The argument is that the forest also serves as a metaphor for *Shakuntala*'s inner world. It reflects her emotions and psychological state of being. As she travels between the forest and the city, her relationship with nature also shifts, symbolizing her journey toward self-discovery and empowerment. This movement between spaces or places mirrors the eco-feminist critique of the separation between humans and nature. It exhibits separation that has led to the degradation of both the environment and women's rights on the Earth.

The Role of Memory

Memory plays a vital role in Gokhale's this novel. Memory is not just a personal tool for self-reflection but as a metaphor for the collective memory of nature and culture. *Shakuntala*'s fragmented memories mirror the fragmented state of the natural world, which has been disrupted and destroyed by human intervention. As Vandana Shiva explains, "the destruction of nature is also the destruction of culture and memory" (Shiva 41). When natural landscapes are degraded, the histories and memories associated with them are lost, severing the connection between past and present.

Gokhale's *Shakuntala* is able to dream of the events of her previous birth and glimpses several images. She reflects on the purpose of life. She starts on to meditate on the philosophical and

religious views on the basic issues of human enquiry: what death is; what life's mysteries are; for what we live; why we die; etc. One of the most pertinent Hindu believe, north Indian in particular, regarding the city of Kashi is: it's a good place to breathe your last breath. She comes to believe that if one dies in Kashi, one becomes liberated from the circle of death and birth. Because of her ability of 'remembering' her previous life, she finds that she is a Vaidya's daughter, and has one-year older mother. She says:

I was named Shakuntala after the heroine of Kalidasa's classic drama. My namesake was not a mortal like me, she was nymph, daughter of the celestial apsara Menaka who seduced the sage Vishwamitra and stole his seed. That Shakuntala had been deserted by her mother, and her birth-father Vishwamitra, and later by her husband Dushyanta – one could say that she carried within herself the samskaras of abandonment. Some even consider it an unlucky name. (Gokhale 6-7)

In this novel, Shakuntala is portrayed as a bold and fearless child. She does not panic while walking alone in the Woods. She is a daughter of 'jungle' in a sense. She has a number of questions in mind like why she is named as Shakuntala but she does not ask them to her mother. She like the Shakuntala of Kalidas grows and wanders up in the area of hills and rills. All day she wanders in the hills without any fear of wild forest animals:

All day I roamed the hills, where the forests abound with --- but I loved the woods, and would return home reluctantly only when the shadows lengthened and the trees whispered like ghostly spirits. I was always cautious, though, and kept to the pathways and clearings. I thought I knew how to stay out of trouble, and was restless to see the world, to wander with the freedom of birds and clouds. (8)

Shakuntala's struggle with her memory parallels the environmental destruction that has erased the histories of natural places. She makes efforts to piece together her fragmented past. She also attempts to reclaim her connection to nature, which has been disrupted by the patriarchal structures that hunt for a control on both she and the environment she lives in. Gokhale writes, "Her memory, like the river, ebbed and flowed, sometimes clear, sometimes murky, always in motion" (Gokhale 83). These examples of fluidity of memory reflect the eco-feminist account of how patriarchal systems have wrecked the relationship between women and nature.

In this novel Shakuntala's memory is not just personal; it is collective. It is encompassing the memories of the natural world and the generations of women who have lived in harmony with the nature. Shakuntala's journey to reclaim her memory is also a journey to reclaim her place within the natural world. It is to reclaim a world that has been damaged by the forces of the patriarchal systems.

The Forest: Space of Feminine Power

The forest in *Shakuntala: The Play of Memory* is more than just a physical boundary. It is a symbolic representation of feminine power and resistance. In many eco-feminist texts, the natural world is depicted as a site of resistance against patriarchal control. It has been expressed as a place where women can find strength and autonomy. The similar is the case with this novel

of Namita Gokhale. In it the forest becomes a refuge for Shakuntala, allowing her to escape the constraints of society and reconnect with her real self.

The correlation between women and nature is a central theme in eco-feminist literature. Gokhale's portrayals of the forest as a breathing space of empowerment for Shakuntala make parallel with this tradition. As Warren argues, "The association of women with nature has historically been used to justify their subordination, but eco-feminists seek to reclaim this connection as a source of strength and resistance" (Warren 122). In this novel, the forest serves as a source of spiritual and emotional strength for Shakuntala. It allows her to transcend the limitations imposed by the rules of man dominated society.

This reclamation of feminine power through nature is also evident in the way Gokhale reviews the traditional mythical stories of Shakuntala. In Kalidasa's version of the myth, Shakuntala is passive recipient of her surroundings. There her fate was determined by the actions of others. In Gokhale's version, in contrast, Shakuntala is an active participant in her own story. She is not passive. She has her own agency of ideas. She uses her connection to nature as a means of reclaiming her identity and agency. This shift in perspective aligns the text with eco-feminist ideals. It emphasizes the importance of women's empowerment. It advocates and asserts the need to resist patriarchal structures that make continuous efforts for dominating both women and the environment.

Subverting the Myth

There may hardly be any debate, now-a-days, that religious myths and stories have been created and used to justify the subjugation of women and nature. Twenty first century feminist and eco-feminist texts are there for subverting the 'norm'. This eco-feminist text aims at reclamation by restating these myths from a new perspective. Eco-feminists seek to challenge the dominant narratives that have perpetuated patriarchal control. In *Shakuntala: The Play of Memory*, Gokhale is engaged in this process of reclamation. She offers a new interpretation of the Shakuntala's myth. She empowers her protagonist and redefines her relationship with the natural world. Gokhale has presented her as a learned lady who has knowledge of 'Dharma' and she is able to identify its attempts of subversion. At a place Shakuntala says, "The Manava Dharma Shastra says: 'A barren wife should be abandoned in the tenth year, one who bears only daughters in the twelfth, and one whose children all die in the fifteenth'" (Gokhale 95).

Kalidas' Shakuntala is portrayed as a passive figure, a victim of a forgetful husband and an unjust society. Her connection to nature is emphasized, but it is ultimately subordinated to her relationship with Dushyanta. Gokhale's Shakuntala's connection to nature becomes a source of strength, allowing her to reclaim her identity and assert her agency.

Warren explains, "Eco-feminism seeks to challenge the dominant patriarchal narratives by reclaiming traditional stories and reinterpreting them from a feminist perspective" (Warren 129). In Gokhale's novel the protagonist's story is not a story of love and loss only. It is a story of empowerment and resistance also. This novel is a story that reflects the broader struggles of women and nature under a regime of patriarchal control.

Shakuntala weds Srijan. He knows her since childhood. Namita Gokhale presents Srijan as a 'mahasaamant'. He is a man of fortune and wealth who is the chief of fourteen villages. The irony is Shakuntala is his third wife. His other two wives are dead. His mother turns towards Buddhism and becomes a nun. For Shakuntala this was not a natural act on part of her mother-in-law. She thinks of her mother-in-law. Some questions were troubling her. Her mind was fully immersed in these questions: Why did she leave the home? What is the reason that she became a nun? She remarks: "She had a husband and a young son, a home and a kitchen. What was she searching for, why did she go away? She spent the rest of her years with faithful Sangha in a monastery. Srijan never talked about his mother, yet her departure must surely have caused him pain" (Gokhale 43).

Srijan's is a rich businessman. He travels a lot. He goes on long business tours. Despite of a happy married life with Shakuntala one day he comes home with another woman: Kamalani. Srijan told Shakuntala that Kamalani is her handmaiden but Shakuntala does not feel good about it. She was able to 'feel' something fishy about it as there was no need of any handmaiden in the home. Presence of Kamalani in home created a tension and the situation brought sense of separation in Shakuntala from Srijan. Actually, Kamalani was another wife of Srijan. Shakuntala felt dejected and helpless as the patriarchal systems stand with man. In Shakuntala's world Men were allowed to have more than one wife at a time. But the presence of Kamalani has certainly shaken her being. She says:

I was not angry with Srijan – he was a man, men were allowed many women, it was the way of the world as I knew it. But the hurt and betrayal, the prickling of thorns under the sheath of my skin – I had never known or anticipated these feelings, just as I had never expected my husband to return from his journey to the east with an exotically beautiful woman with cold and mocking eyes. (Gokhale 58)

Gokhale has successfully expressed male domination in the society. In this novel Shakuntala is as a seeker who follows the way of her fate without looking back and reaches Kashi, the holy city to search her own self. An entire world of meaning is discovered in her exploration of what the idea of Shakuntala can open up. When Shakuntala runs away from home, she finds refuge in a cave with a woman who introduces her to the mysteries and powers of the mother-goddess. The woman says, "Remember that in every one of her forms the goddess is always Swamini, mistress of herself" (35). She further says, "You must be strong, Shakuntala, there is little place in your world for strong women, but none for the weak" (36).

Conclusion

Namita Gokhale's *Shakuntala: The Play of Memory* is a affluent and mysterious account that offers a compelling exploration of feminist and eco-feminist themes. The portrayal of Shakuntala's connection to nature, her struggle with memory, and her reclamation of feminine power, the novel assess critically the structures and rules of the present. The novel challenges the traditional and mythical narratives that have made attempts in the name of 'traditions' to justify the exploitation of women and nature. It offers a vision of empowerment and resistance. With the

help of Shakuntala's journey toward self-discovery and empowerment Gokhale reflects the eco-feminist voice for a review of the relationship between humans and the natural world.

Gokhale converts a mute woman into a talking woman. She has provides her strength and means to articulate the silence of women. Gokhale depicts the suffering, distress and conflict of Indian women who are caught between patriarchy and tradition. She also voices their attempts of individuality, self expression and independence in a unique way in this novel.

Limitations and Future Research

The scope of this study is constrained to the fictional writings in Indian context that relates to the subjugation of both the women and the nature. This is to argue that the women writers are particularly more inclined to identify and relate themselves with the pains of subjugations and exploitations that prevail in the society against the women and the nature at large. Namita Gokhale's *Shakuntala: The Play of Memory*, published in 2005 is glanced from an eco-feminist approach. This novel however may be approached from other perspectives of the literary analysis. This paper focuses on how the protagonist deals with the challenges poised in front of her by the patriarchy and how her challenges are similar to that of the nature. It is therefore to be asserted that the results or findings of this paper may not be representative of the entire community that reads the novel. Therefore, for the future, it is proposed that the novel is to be read from an individual's own view point.

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